

STOCHASTIC MODELING OF OPTION PRICING: INSIGHTS FROM THE BLACK-SCHOLES FRAMEWORK FOR ECONOMIC INVESTMENTS

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Abstract

This paper considered an option pricing model which could be used for decision making in stock trading business. In particular, we studied the Black-Scholes model of European option which gave closed form prices of Call and Put option prices with disparities of some statistical parameters affecting real life changes. The Quantiles-Quantiles (Q-Q) normality tests were considered on Call and Put options prices which showed that they are significantly correlated and normally distributed. We also conducted hypothesis testing via Kolmogorov Smirnov (KS) and result violated an assumption of Black-Scholes that stipulated that volatility is constant throughout the trading days and graphical result were used to authenticate the violation of Black-Scholes model of option pricing. The results obtained here has profound financial benefits for economic investments.

Keywords: Call and Put options, Stock prices, Stochastic Analysis, KS and Q-Q.

1.1 Introduction

A stock in an investment simply means a share in the possession of an integrated corporation. A stock shows proof of ownership. Investors pay money for stocks with anticipation that it will give returns from dividends and either appreciate, or grow in value. Thus, market price is the current price by which an asset or service can be bought or sold. Economic hypothesis agrees that the market prices meet at a spot where the driving force of supply and demand rally. In stock market the dynamics of stock prices are reflected by unsure movement of their value over time. According to [16], one potential reason for the random behavior of the asset price is the Efficient Market (EMH) Hypothesis. The EMH mainly states two things as follows: (a) the past of a stock price is completely reflected in present prices. (b) The markets react right away to any latest information about a particular stock. These assumptions mean that changes in the stock price follow a random walk. These two assumptions imply that changes in the stock depend only on its recent price.

In financial markets, investors and financial analysts are generally too interested on how to maximize profit over particular trading days, that is, the changes in the price of goods and services. Therefore, modeling a behavior of a stock exchange market can be made through its relative change of the unstable market variables in time so as to predict stock price fluctuation,

advice investors and corporative owners who are working out for convenient Ways to do business by issuing of stocks in their corporations.

This paper is about option pricing and some of its dynamics in financial markets via valuation using Black-Scholes (BS) model of option pricing as it explores the changes of option (values) as a function of security and time. An option is a tool whose worth is derived from the principal asset which is otherwise known as financial derivative. This type of derivative does have anything in common with mathematical meaning of derivative. In other words, an option on underlying asset is a business between parties who come together to agree on either buying or selling an underlying asset at a determined strike price in the future for a fixed price; [3]. The cost of the option lies on the underlying asset, which is usually a stock, commodity, currency or an index, Kwok (2008). The holder has the right but cannot be compelled to buy, for call option where European put option involves the ability to sell an asset for a certain charge at a prescribed date in the future. The holder has the right but cannot be compelled to buy, for call option where European put option involves the ability to sell an asset for a certain charge at a prescribed date in the future.

Many scholars have used Black-Scholes Equation in divers way. For instance; [3] considered Black-Scholes partial differential equation on stock market prices for both analytic and numerical. In another scenario [2] focused on the Black-Scholes terminal value problem and provided its solutions through the Laplace transform. More so, [9] proposed a framework based on the celebrated transform of Mellin type (MT) for the analytic solution of the Black-Scholes Merton European Power Put Option Model (BSMEPPOM) on Dividend Yield (DY) with Modified-Log-Power Payoff Function (MLPPF) under the geometric Brownian motion. In the same vein, [4] analyzed BS formula for the valuation of European options; hermit polynomials were applied. They concluded that BS formula can easily be achieved devoid of the use of partial differential equation. In the work of [5], time varying factor were incorporated in the explicit formula for different aspect of options with the aim of providing exact solution for dividend paying equity of option. In considering the stability of stock market price of stochastic model, [6] applied Crank-Nicolson numerical scheme to BS model. The results showed stock prices being stable and its increasing rate of stock shares was obtained. Not quite long, [7] investigated the variation of stock market price using BS PDE. The convergence to equilibrium of growth rate and sufficient conditions for stability was achieved. Lots of scholars has written extensively to mention but a few: [10], [11] and [15] etc.

The key problem of investors is unable to take an appropriate decision when using BlackScholes model of option pricing. These problems may have arisen due to its assumptions. For instance, volatility is constant throughout the trading days This inconsistency may lead to Black-Scholes largely not predicting the Call and Put options for decision making; which may not benefit the interest of option traders.

In order to tackle the problem posed by [1], stating hypothesis testing to properly examine European options and to violate the Black-Scholes assumption on volatility being constant throughout the trading days; which has given a lot of concern to many option traders and society at large. Hence, this paper compliments the work of [8].

This paper is prearranged as follows: Section 2.1 is material and methods, Section 3.1, Results and discussion of findings while the paper is concluded in 4.1.

2.1 Material Methods

In this paper, we review all relevant stochastic methods that would help in achieving the derivation. Firstly, our focus in Section 2.2 that would lead to stochastic differential equation, which gave rise to Black Scholes model of option.

2.2. Stochastic Differential Equation (SDE)

Stochastic differential equation is a differential equation with stochastic term. Therefore, assume that (Ω, \mathcal{F}) is a probability space with filtration $\{\mathcal{F}_t\}_{t \in [0, T]}$ and

$W_t = (W_t^1, W_t^2, \dots, W_t^m)^T, t \in [0, T]$ an m-dimensional brownian motion on the given probability space. We have SDE in coefficient functions of f and g as follows

$$dX_t = f(t, X_t)dt + g(t, X_t)dZ_t, 0 \leq t \leq T,$$

$$X(0) = x_0,$$

Where $T \in [0, \infty)$, x_0 is an n-dimensional random variable and coefficient functions are in the form $f: [0, T] \times \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$ and $g: [0, T] \times \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{n \times m}$. SDE can also be written in the form of integral as follows:

$$X_t = x_0 + \int_0^t f(s, X_s)ds + \int_0^t g(s, X_s)dZ_s, \quad (1)$$

Where dX, dZ , are terms known as stochastic differentials. The Z_t is a valued stochastic process $X(t)$.

However, let $S(t)$ be the price of some risky asset at time t , and r , an expected rate of returns on the stock and dt as a relative change during the trading days such that the stock follows a random walk which is govern by a stochastic differential equation.

$$dS(t) = rS(t)dt + \sigma S(t)dW(t) \quad (1)$$

Theorem 3.1: (Ito’s formula) Let $(\Omega, \mathcal{F}, \mathbb{P})$ be a filtered probability space $X = \{X_t, t \in [0, T]\}$ be an adaptive stochastic process on $(\Omega, \mathcal{F}, \mathbb{P})$ possessing a quadratic variation $\langle X \rangle$ with SDE defined as:

$$dX_t = g(t, X_t)dt + f(t, X_t)dW_t \quad \text{and for } u = u(t, X_t) \in C^1$$

$$du(t, X_t) = \frac{\partial u}{\partial t} dt + \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} f(t, X_t) dt + \frac{1}{2} f^2 \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2} dt + \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} g(t, X_t) dW_t$$

Using theorem 3.1 and equation (1) comfortably solves the SDE with a solution given below:

$$S_t = S_0 \exp\left(\int_0^t \left(\mu - \frac{1}{2}\sigma^2\right) dt + \int_0^t \sigma dW_t\right) \quad [0,1]$$

2.2 The Black-Scholes Model

This model is commonly used in financial modeling and has had great impact on contemporary research in Mathematics of finance. The Black-Scholes model is made up of on seven assumptions:

- The asset price has characteristics of a Brownian motion with μ and σ as constants.
- The transaction costs or taxes are not allowed.
- The entire securities are absolutely divisible.
- Dividend is not permitted during the period of the derivatives.
- Unacceptable of riskless arbitrage opportunities.
- The security trading is constant.
- The option is exercised at the time of expiry for both call and put options.

In mathematical finance, an arbitrage argument show that any derivative $V(S,t)$ written on v must satisfy the partial differential equation of the form of option pricing; hence we have the following:

$$\frac{\partial V(S,t)}{\partial t} + \frac{1}{2}\sigma^2 S^2 \frac{\partial^2 V(S,t)}{\partial S^2} + rS \frac{\partial V(S,t)}{\partial S} - rV(S,t) = 0 \tag{2}$$

+

$$\frac{\partial V(S,t)}{\partial S} = 0$$

Where r represents interest rate, σ represents volatility of the underlying assets and t represents time of maturity. With boundary conditions:

$$V(S,t) \rightarrow \text{as } S \rightarrow \infty \text{ on } [0,T] \tag{3}$$

$$V(S,t) \rightarrow 0 \text{ as } S \rightarrow 0 \text{ on } [0,T] \tag{4}$$

And final time condition given by :

$$V(S,T) = (S - k)^+ = f(S) \text{ on } [0,\infty] \tag{5}$$

Equation (4) is the value of asset is worthless when the stock price is zero. To eliminate the price process in

$$C = S \Phi(d_1) - Ke^{-rt} \Phi(d_2) \tag{1}$$

$$d_1 = \frac{\ln \left(\frac{S}{K} \right) + \left(r + \frac{\sigma^2}{2} \right) t}{\sigma \sqrt{t}} \tag{6}$$

$$d_2 = d_1 - \sigma \sqrt{t}$$

slightly gives the Black-Scholes analytic formula for the prices of European call option is given as follows

σ

K

t

where C is Price of a call option, S is price of underlying asset, K is the strike price, r is the riskless rate, t is time to maturity, σ^2 is variance of underlying asset, σ is standard deviation of the (generally referred to as volatility) underlying asset, and N is the cumulative normal distribution.

Similarly Black-Scholes analytic formula for the prices of European Putl option is given as follows

$$P = Ke^{-rt} \Phi(-d_2) - S \Phi(-d_1) \tag{7}$$

$$d_1 = \frac{\ln \left(\frac{S}{K} \right) + \left(r + \frac{\sigma^2}{2} \right) t}{\sigma \sqrt{t}}$$

$$d_2 = d_1 - \sigma \sqrt{t}$$

where P is the

price of a put option and the meaning of other parameters remain the same as in (6) [12-13].

2.3 Volatility constant of Black-Scholes Assumption in real life Trading

Black-Scholes model assumes that volatility is constant throughout the trading days. This assertion can be verified using statistical hypothesis testing to this end, we defined volatility as follows.

The volatility, σ : let S_i represent each of the initial stock prices at the end of i -th trading period, $T = -t, t_{i-1}, i$

σ 1. we define it as the logarithm of the daily return on each of four compartments of stock prices such that:

$$\sigma_i = \ln \left(\frac{S_i}{S_{i-1}} \right) \tag{8}$$

σ

The mean of each of stock prices are given as

$$1_n \tag{9}$$

$$\mu = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n u_i$$

$N_{i=1}$

The standard deviation is given as

$$\sigma = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n-1} \sum_{i=1}^n (u_i - \mu)^2} \quad v = i \tag{10}$$

$n - 1$

The volatility of the daily stock return:

v

$$\sigma = \frac{1}{\sqrt{v}} \tag{11}$$

σ

2.4. Kolmogorov-Smirnov (KS) Goodness of fit test for Call and Put option H_0 : Stock volatility is constant throughout the trading days for Call and Put options.

H_1 : Stock volatility is not constant throughout the trading days for Call and Put options. With 0.01 percent level of significance.

3.1 Results and Discussion of Findings

This Section presents results from our proposed model for Call and Put options whose closed form prices are displayed through simulation below:

Table 1.1: The fair value of Call option with variations of statistical constraints when the initial stock prices are 40, 50,60 and 70 with $K = 25$, $r = 0.2$ and $T = 1$

<i>Sigma</i>	<i>S₀ =40 BS Exact values</i>	<i>S₀ =50 BS Ex act values</i>	<i>S₀ =60 BS Exact values</i>	<i>S₀ = 70 BS Exact values</i>	<i>Mean E X(t)</i>
0.25	19.5398	29.4815	39.5317	49.5317	34.5212
0.3	19.5695	29.3841	39.5322	49.5318	34.5044
0.35	19.6371	29.2378	39.5353	49.5325	34.4857
0.4	19.7508	29.0650	39.5469	49.5361	34.4747
0.45	19.9117	28.8896	39.5750	49.5476	34.4810
0.5	20.1167	28.7302	39.6277	49.5736	34.5121
0.55	20.3607	28.5990	39.7106	49.6208	34.5728
0.6	20.6383	28.5022	39.8273	49.6946	34.6656
0.65	20.9441	28.4420	39.9788	49.7985	34.7908
0.7	21.2733	28.4178	40.1643	49.9342	34.9474
0.75	21.6219	28.4269	40.3820	50.1020	35.1332
0.8	21.9861	28.4655	40.6295	50.3009	35.3455

Table 1.2: The fair value of Call option with variations of statistical constraints when the initial stock prices are 40, 50,60 and 70 with K = 100, r = 0.2 and T = 1.

Sigma	$S_0=40$	$S_0=50$	$S_0=60$	$S_0=70$	Mean $EX(t)$
	BS Exact values	BS Exact values	BS Exact values	BS Exact values	
0.25	41.8817	32.0183	22.7672	14.9160	27.8958
0.3	41.9211	32.2717	23.4960	16.1862	28.4688
0.35	42.0213	32.6694	24.3677	17.5121	29.1426
0.4	42.2025	33.1966	25.3408	18.8713	29.9028
0.45	42.4721	33.8322	26.3860	20.2504	30.7352
0.5	42.8277	34.5553	27.4826	21.6405	31.6265
0.55	43.2622	35.3479	28.6158	23.0357	32.5654
0.6	43.7659	36.1951	29.7745	24.4317	33.5418
0.65	44.3292	37.0850	30.9508	25.8252	34.5476
0.7	44.9429	38.0079	32.1384	27.2137	35.5757
0.75	45.5988	38.9559	33.3325	28.5950	36.6206
0.8	46.2893	39.9226	34.5291	29.9675	37.6771

Increase in sigma increases the value of Call and Put options prices. When sigma of an underlying asset increases, it generally leads to an increase in the value of both Call and Put options. This is because higher volatility increases the potential for large movement in the underlying asset price, which increases the likelihood that the options will end up in-the-money at expiration. Furthermore, in terms of corporate investor, an increase in sigma can provide both opportunities and risk: corporate investors who are bearish on a particular asset may Put options to hedge against potential losses. See Tables 1.1-1.2 in columns 1-5. This result is in line with Nwobi et al. (2021) and Nwobi et al. (2019) etc.

Tables 1.1, 1.2 columns 6-8 predicts as follows: The mean of Call and Put option values are used to assess the general sentiment of the market towards a particular security. For example, if the mean of Call option values is higher the mean of Put option values, it indicates that traders are bullish on the security.

Figure 1.1: Quantiles-Quantiles (QQ) normality test of Call option when initial stock price is 40 and 50.

Figure 1.2: Quantiles-Quantiles (QQ) normality test of Call option when initial stock price is 60 and 70.

Figure 1.3: Quantiles-Quantiles (QQ) normality test of Put option when initial stock price is 40 and 50.

Figure 1.4: Quantiles-Quantiles (QQ) normality test of Put option when initial stock price is 60 and 70.

More so, it can be seen in Figures 1.1-1.4 that the QQ plot indicates that the two Call and Put option prices comes from a common distribution. They are statistically significant, correlated and have lots of financial benefits hence it waves around the normal distribution.

Table 1.3: Stock Market Parameters with their respective values

Year	Trading days	Initial stock prices	Volatility
2014	252	45.40	0.4127
2015	252	36.18	0.7843
2016	251	40.91	0.2906
2017	251	25.61	0.4061
2018	253	23.72	0.3696
2019	252	12.85	0.7579
2020	252	17.10	0.4214

2021	252	16.75	0.2951
2022	251	16.29	0.3964
2023	252	20.08	0.3011
2024	96	30.59	0.4428

1.1.2 Kolmogorov-Smirnov (KS) Goodness of fit test for Call and Put option H_0 : Stock volatility is constant throughout the trading days for Call and Put options.

H_1 : Stock volatility is not constant throughout the trading days for Call and Put options.

The KS test shows that volatility is not constant throughout the trading day which violates one of the assumptions of Black-Scholes model of option pricing with $\alpha = 0.01$ level of significant. This can have important implications for option traders as volatility is one of the key factors in determining the price of an option.

Figure 1.5: Volatility trend of stock prices over time

Figure 1.5 shows the pictorial movement of volatility over time as the trend is not steady. The different change seen is due to the direction of volatility. It causes higher and lower option prices depending the direction of volatility change. This is to attest that volatility is not constant in realworld market which is in agreement to our statistical hypothesis.

4.1. Conclusion

In this study the Black-Scholes model of European option were considered herein, which gave closed form prices of Call and Put option prices with disparities of some statistical parameters affecting real life changes for capital market. The Call and Put option prices were further transformed by exploring the properties of

covariance and correlation matrix solution to analyze and predict investment plans for capital market. To this end, results show as follows:(i) increase in sigma increases the value of Call and Put option prices (ii)Black-Scholes assumption on volatility were violated through Kolmogorov Smirnov test (v) Q-Q normality test were significantly correlated and normally distributed, However, the volatility assumptions in BS model which was violated in our hypothesis does not in any way mean that the model is unacceptable; there should be a continuous research, picking tools from Mathematics and Statistics to validate the Black and Scholes efforts of 1973.

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